

8T – Doing Physics on Hilbert Space is Wrong

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Abstract:

By analyzing the setting in which QM is analyzed on, i.e. Hilbert space and the setting in which the 8T is analyzed on a varying Lorentz manifold, there could be certain contradictions of physical results such as the coupling magnitudes or the outward time invariant acceleration. In particular, if each point in space is a function, where could be points that causes the rules of physics to be different in each point.

Introduction

The QM framework is analyzed on Hilbert space. That space is unique as it is a space which allocate each point a function of certain sort. The setting in which Einstein work on is a manifold (M, g) with $(3,1)$ signature. Those spaces are very different. First, Hilbert space as one came to believe do not indicate connectedness. Second, if each point is a function, in order to describe the behavior of space-time in large scale we would need to specify the entire spectra of composing functions, which is impossible to do. There could be points, i.e. functions which are different and contradicting the coupling constants series, there could be a function that associate a boson to non-integer numbers and not to prime numbers, and so that is another law of nature, and as far as we know it's wrong.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

To emphasize the point in the previous paragraph we can vary the original condition of the isomorphism between primes and bosonic fields and associate each number which do not belong to the prime a bosonic field. That is against what we know, however if each point is a function there could be a function of that sort. Such an analysis is revealing the weakness and the absurdness of such a space. In other words, such space give rise to infinite amount of laws of physics. That is in contrast to Einstein theory and the new 8T that built upon one set of rules, not just for this universe but also to every-universe.

$$N_V \notin \mathbb{P} \cup (+1);$$

$$\mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{the Set of Primes}$$

Such space could also cause to a variation of the main equation at certain points:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \rightarrow \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^K g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$K \neq 2$$

Alternatively, there could be points on that Hilbert space where:

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \neq \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2}$$

Defying Einstein equivalence principle, such points would than deteriorate the notion of the entire insights gather so far, as it would imply no laws of nature or infinite amount of laws of nature, two different ways to state the same thing. Physics cannot be done on the Hilbert space. By recent development of the coupling series on a varying manifold, it is no longer needed. QM is encompassed on the varying matric tensor, the electron is the majestic (3) and the net curvature are discrete numbers isomorphic to primes or one. It is possible to elevate all that we know about QM to a simpler setting Einstein and Lorentz worked on.

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta \gamma_i > 0 \quad (3.1)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "The Coupling constants series, Spin Symmetries and Unbounded electrons" In: (2021)
- [3] O. Manor. "Proving Einstein Wrong – Gravity is a Short Range Interaction" In: (2021)